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Predictive Role of Religiosity on Marital Duration among Couples in Ibadan Baptist Conference, Oyo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The growing challenges on marital cohesion in contemporary society and the increasing rates of divorce have become major concerns particularly in religious communities. This study therefore examines the predictive role of Religiosity on

marital duration among couples within the Ibadan Baptist conference, Nigeria. The study aims to identify religious factors that contribute to enduring and satisfying marital relationships. Descriptive survey research design was adopted, employing a quantitative approach. A total of 600 married individuals (300 couples) through stratified random sampling across various Baptist congregations in Ibadan, using a multistage sampling procedure. Data was collected using validated instruments: a religiosity scale measuring religious commitment and practices, and a marital duration scale assessing perceived relationship durability and satisfaction. Findings from multiple regression analysis indicate that religiosity significantly predict marital duration, When considering the total dimensions of Religiosity, a significant positive correlation with marital duration was observed ($r = 0.561, p < 0.001$). This indicates significant positive relationships between various aspects of religiosity and marital duration. It also shows that higher levels of religiosity are associated with longer and more stable marriages, likely due to shared values, community support, and faith-based coping mechanisms. The study concludes that a religious compatibility plays a crucial role in sustaining durable marriages. It recommends integrating religious assessment and faith-based counseling into marital support programs within religious institution. These insights provide valuable implications for church leaders, marriage counselors, and policy makers seeking to strengthen marital relationships in faith-based contexts.

Keywords: Religiosity, Marital Duration, Couples

Introduction

Marriage is a vital social and spiritual institution that contributes significantly to personal fulfillment, societal stability, and upbringing of future generations. A successful and enduring marriage not only promotes emotional well-being for the couple but also provides a stable foundation for children and the community at large (Huston, 2022). However, in recent years, the increasing prevalence of marital breakdowns, separations, and divorce has raised concern, even within faith-based communities where high moral standards and spiritual values are emphasized. The increasing rates of divorce, separation, domestic violence and marital dissatisfaction have become a cause for concern for researchers, policymakers, and religious leaders. According to Laurence (2020), studies have shown that marriages provide unique benefits for a man, woman and the children from the marital union. It ensures accessibility of children to both mother and father whose joint efforts contribute significantly to their upbringing and development as the future member of the society.

In Christian contexts, particularly within Baptist settings like Ibadan Baptist conference, Oyo State, Nigerian, marriage is viewed as a sacred covenant ordained by God. Despite consistent biblical teaching and church support structures at nurturing marital relationships, challenges persist. Many couples struggle to maintain their marriages over time, suggesting that spiritual guidance alone may not be sufficient alone to ensure marital longevity. This has prompted a growing interest in identifying the psychological and spiritual factors that influence how long marriages last.

Conceptual Framework

Concept of Religiosity: According to Dada (2021), the key factor widely acknowledged to impact marital relationships is religiosity. On the other hand, Laurence (2020) defined religiosity as the depth of an individual's religious beliefs, practices, and commitment has been shown to influence marital attitudes, values, and coping mechanisms. In Christian settings, religious teachings emphasize commitment, forgiveness, mutual respect, and the sanctity of marriage. Couples who share strong religious convictions and engage in shared spiritual practices often report higher levels of marital duration and satisfaction. The studies also show that the state of being religious affects marriage stability (Hardy and Carlo, 2020). The couples must be more adjusted the more extended the actual number of years they have been together in being religious. Marital success is expected to be facilitated by the religion activity.

Concept of Marital Duration: Osiki (2022), defines marital duration as the length of a couple remains in marriage; it is the number of years couples spent

together. Studies indicate that marital durability or marital stability may be positively or negatively correlated with religiosity (Langlais et al, 2022). Couples who have been married for longer are more mature and adaptable. The marriage lifespan is fundamental since family length is one of the most important factors for family fulfillment or durability. The partners must be more adjusted the more extended the actual number of years they have been together. Marital success is expected to be facilitated by the duration of marriage. Marital durability is said to be a social problem. It affects a significant number of people in the world today (Hardy et al, 2020). Therefore, it demands urgent attention considering the bad effects it has on the society in general.

According to Onwuasoanya, (2022), Marriage, as both a social and spiritual institution, is expected to provide companionship, stability, and mutual support. However, in recent years, the durability of marriages, has come under threat. Reports of marital dissatisfaction, emotional separation, and increasing cases of divorce raise critical questions about the factors that contribute to marital longevity among Christian couples. Religion also influences many activities beyond the purely religious sphere, including the education and upbringing of children, the allocation of time and money, the cultivation of social relationships, the development of business and professional networks, and even the choice of place of residence. Clearly, household sin which the partners differ in their preferences and objectives in this area would be characterized by reduced efficiency and potentially more conflict.

Other things being equal, the complementarity of religion as a marital trait implies that heterogamous unions would display more instability than homogenous unions. Yet compatibility between partners of different faiths may vary with the specific religions involved, depending in part on the similarity in beliefs and practices of the two religions, and in part on the mutual tolerance embodied in their respective doctrines. Some view religious groups as ranging along an "exclusivist-ecumenical" continuum defined by the clarity with which they draw their membership a boundary. At one extreme, "exclusivist" religious groups are those with clear, strictly enforced membership criteria, frequently with proscriptions against out-marriage and sometimes even shunning of nonmembers. At the other extreme, "ecumenical" groups tend to have few membership criteria, often vaguely stated and weakly enforced, and place relatively little importance on religious group boundaries (Langlais et al, 2022). The location of the spouses' religions along this continuum would influence the stability of the marriage: the closer to the ecumenical end of the spectrum, the less the marital stress and hence instability that can be expected. Other dimensions of religious doctrine and ritual have implications not only for the

consequences of out-marriage but also for differences in stability across various types of homogenous unions. Religions differ in the importance of family-centered ritual (as distinct from that which is either individual or church-centered), as well as in the compatibility between their practices and beliefs and the customs in the larger society. For religious groups in which such compatibility is low and the role of the family is central, interfaith unions are expected to be highly stable, and the destabilizing effects of out-marriage particularly pronounced. (Botwin et, al, 2021)

In addition, relatively high costs of dissolution and correspondingly high marital stability are expected for homogenous marriages involving religions with proscriptions against divorce. Apart from differences between religious groups, variations in preferences among individuals and couples also play a role. Couples differ in the weight they place on shared activities, including religious observance, and individuals differ in the priority they give to religion and to religious compatibility as a marital trait. These factors influence the degree to which differences in religious beliefs and practices affect stability adversely. Similarly, the extent to which religious complementarities are a stabilizing force for a homogenous marriage depends in part on the importance attached to religion by each of the spouses (Bramlett, 2019).

Despite this known factor, limited research has explored how religiosity predicts marital duration, especially within specific religious communities in Nigeria, most studies focus on marital satisfaction and stability but neglect the actual length of time couples remain married.

Statement of the Problem

In recent years, the durability of marriages, even within Christian settings like the Ibadan Baptist Conference, has come under threat. Reports of marital dissatisfaction, emotional separation, and increasing cases of divorce raise critical questions about the factors that contribute to marital longevity among Christian couples. Despite regular church teachings, marital seminars, and biblical exhortations promoting unity and commitment, some marriages still experience early breakdown. This contradiction suggests that spiritual guidance alone may not be sufficient to ensure lasting marriages. It is therefore important to explore the underlying spiritual factors that contribute to how long marriages endure. This study, therefore, seeks to fill this gap by examining how religiosity predicts marital duration among couples in the Ibadan Baptist Conference. The findings are expected to inform pastors, counselors, and Christian marriage educators about the psychological dimensions that contribute to lasting marriages, ultimately strengthening marital support systems within the church.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to explore the predictive roles of Religiosity on marital duration among couples in Ibadan Baptist Conference, Oyo State, Nigeria. Specific Objectives are to:

1. Examine the relationship between religiosity and marital duration of the study participants.
2. Determine the predictive effect of religiosity on marital duration of the study participants.

Research Question

1. What is the relationship between religiosity and marital duration among couples in Ibadan Baptist Conference?
2. What are the predictive effects of religiosity on marital duration among couples in Ibadan Baptist Conference?

Methodology

This research adopted descriptive survey research design. It is experimental research design. The research was used because it is appropriate for the answering of research questions. The population for this study comprised all the married couples in Ibadan Baptist Conference of the Nigerian Baptist Convention. Ibadan Baptist Conference is within the Ibadan metropolis. The sample for the study engaged 300 registered couples of the population (i.e. 600 participants) using multistage sampling procedure. At the first stage, purposive sampling technique is used to select Ibadan Baptist Conference as the study area. At the second stage, systematic random sampling technique was used to select 10 Associations out of the 20 Associations in the Conference within each stratum. At the third stage, simple random sampling technique was used to select 3 churches from each of the selected Associations totaling 30 churches in the Conference. At the last stage, 10 couples (i.e., 20 participants) were drawn from each of the 30 churches selected for the study.

Two standardized instruments were used; Revised Dyadic Adjustment Scale (RDAS) is a self-report measure that is used to assess couple marital relationships in terms of marital adjustment, quality, satisfaction and, marital stability. RDAS is a 14-item questionnaire adapted by Busby, Crane, Larson and Christensen (1995) and Dimensions of Religiosity Scale was used, DRS is a 20-item scale adapted by Joseph and DiDuca (2007), as a new version of 24-item. Dimensions of Religiosity Scale (DR Scale) developed by DiDuca and Joseph (1997) to measure four dimensions of religious thinking and behavior

Data collected from the questionnaire were carefully scored and analysed. Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) 21.0 versions was utilised for the analysis. Descriptive statistics including frequencies, percentages, means, weighted means and standard deviations were used to analyse and to address the research questions raised from the study

Results and Discussion

Research Question One: What are the predictive effects of religiosity on marital duration among couples in Ibadan Baptist Conference?

Table 1: Pearson Correlation of Religiosity and Marital Duration Indicators

Religiosity / Marital Duration		Consensus	Satisf action	Cohes ion	Total Marital Duration
Preoccupati on	Pearson Correlation	.416**	.436**	.246**	.472**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
	N	600	600	600	600
Guidance	Pearson Correlation	.528**	.484**	.369**	.600**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
	N	600	600	600	600
Conviction	Pearson Correlation	.351**	.222**	.362**	.417**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
	N	600	600	600	600
Emotional Involvement	Pearson Correlation	.446**	.460**	.212**	.479**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
	N	600	600	600	600

Total Dimensions of Religiosity	Pearson Correlation	.494**	.441**	.354**	.561**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
	N	600	600	600	600

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Researchers' Fieldwork, 2025

The Pearson correlation analysis was conducted to investigate the relationship between religiosity and marital duration among couples in the Ibadan Baptist Conference. The results revealed that all dimensions of religiosity (Preoccupation, Guidance, Conviction, Emotional Involvement, and Total Dimension of Religiosity) were positively and significantly correlated with all measures of Marital Duration (Consensus, Satisfaction, Cohesion and Total Marital Duration). Specifically, Preoccupation was positively correlated with Total Marital Duration ($r = 0.472, p < 0.001$), while Guidance showed a stronger positive correlation ($r = 0.600, p < 0.001$). Conviction was also positively correlated with Total Marital Duration ($r = 0.417, p < 0.001$), as was Emotional involvement ($r = 0.479, p < 0.001$). When considering the Total Dimensions of Religiosity, a significant positive correlation with Total Marital Duration was observed ($r = 0.561, p < 0.001$). These results indicate significant positive relationships between various aspects of religiosity and marital duration (Table 1).

Research Question Two: To what extent is the relationship between religiosity and marital duration among couples in Ibadan Baptist Conference?

Table 2: Multiple linear regression table of Religiosity and Marital Duration

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Squared	Adjusted R Squared	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F	df1	df2	Sig.
1	.610a	0.372	0.368	5.2072	0.372	88.07	4	5	<0.001

a Predictors: (Constant), Total Dimensions of Religiosity, Conviction, Guidance, Emotional Involvement

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	9552.023	4	2388.006	88.07	.000
	Residual	16133.36	595	27.115		
	Total	25685.39	599			

a Dependent Variable: Total Marital Duration
b Predictors: (Constant), Total Dimensions of Religiosity, Conviction, Guidance, Emotional Involvement

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	16.774	2.618		6.406	<0.001
	Guidance	1.944	0.311	0.596	6.249	<0.001
	Conviction	0.373	0.193	0.181	1.939	0.053
	Emotional Involvement	0.534	0.313	0.163	1.709	0.088
	Total Dimensions of Religiosity	-0.201	0.176	-0.248	-1.142	0.254

a Dependent Variable: Total Marital Duration

		Excluded Variables ^a				
Model		Beta In	T	Sig.	Partial Correlation	Collinearity Statistics
1	Preoccupation	.000b	0	1	0	0

a Dependent Variable: Total Marital Duration
b Predictors in the Model: (Constant), Total Dimensions of Religiosity, Conviction, Guidance, Emotional Involvement

Significant level at $p < 0.05$
 Source: Researchers' Fieldwork, 2025

Multiple linear regression analysis was conducted to examine the extent relationship between dimensions of religiosity and marital duration among couples in the Ibadan Baptist Conference. The regression model was statistically significant, $F(4, 595) = 88.07, p < 0.001$, explaining 37.2% of the variance in marital duration ($R^2 = 0.372, \text{Adjusted } R^2 = 0.368$). Among the predictors, guidance showed a significant positive effect on marital duration ($\beta = 0.596, p < 0.001$). Conviction had a positive but marginally non-significant effect ($\beta = 0.181, p = 0.053$). Emotional involvement also showed a positive but non-significant relationship with marital duration ($\beta = 0.163, p = 0.088$). The total dimensions of religiosity did not significantly predict marital duration ($\beta = -0.248, p = 0.254$) (Table 1).

Preoccupation was automatically excluded by SPSS during the analysis which could be due to multicollinearity (two or more predictors in the model are highly correlated, making it difficult to isolate their individual effects on the dependent variable) (Table 2).

These results suggest that guidance is the strongest and only significant predictor of marital duration among the religiosity dimensions in this model.

Discussion of Findings

The Pearson correlation analysis demonstrated that all dimensions of religiosity; preoccupation, guidance, conviction, emotional involvement, and the overall religiosity score were positively correlated with marital duration. This aligns with previous studies that have showed the importance of religious involvement in promoting marital stability. For instance, (Huston, 2022)

emphasized the role of religiosity in enhancing marital cohesion and satisfaction by providing couples with a sense of shared purpose and values. The significant correlations found in this study, particularly with the dimensions of guidance and preoccupation, suggest that religious engagement, which often involves seeking guidance and deeply engaging in spiritual practices, may help couples navigate marital challenges and promote longevity in their relationships.

From the regression analysis, the finding that guidance had the strongest positive correlation with marital duration corroborates the work of, who highlighted the role of religious guidance as a crucial element in marital stability. Religious guidance often provides a framework for couples to resolve conflicts, make decisions together, and strengthen their emotional bond. In this study, guidance emerged as the only significant predictor of marital duration in the regression analysis, reinforcing the idea that couples who seek and receive religious guidance are more likely to experience enduring marriages. This aligns with the findings of Langlais et al, (2022), who found that couples who prioritize religious guidance have a stronger sense of marital commitment and a higher capacity for overcoming relational difficulties.

The marginally non-significant effects of conviction and emotional involvement on marital duration are noteworthy. While these dimensions were positively correlated with marital duration in the initial correlation analysis, their lack of significance in the regression model suggests that other factors, such as religious guidance, may be more directly influential in predicting marital longevity. However, in this context, it appears that while conviction and emotional involvement contribute to marital satisfaction, they may not directly affect marital duration as strongly as guidance does. It may be that emotional involvement is more closely tied to day-to-day marital satisfaction, which is not always reflected in the long-term stability of the relationship.

Additionally, the total dimensions of religiosity did not significantly predict marital duration in the regression model, despite its significant correlation with marital duration in the Pearson analysis. This suggests that while a general sense of religiosity appears to influence the duration of marriage, it may be the specific dimensions of religiosity, particularly guidance, that play a more direct role. This finding is in line with other studies that observed that while religiosity as a broad construct is positively related to marital stability, specific religious practices and beliefs are more influential in determining marital outcomes.

Conclusion

The findings from this study suggest that marital duration among couples in the Ibadan Baptist Conference is shaped by religiosity the study adds a distinctive viewpoint to the role of religiosity by demonstrating strong evidence that religious practices and beliefs are closely related to marital duration. The study finds that some aspects of religiosity, like prayer frequency, belief in Christ, and adherence to biblical teachings, have significant correlations with factors like marital regret, the frequency of arguments, and even the likelihood of discussing divorce. The results of the study provide a useful framework for learning how societal, religious, and personal factors interact to influence marital stability, particularly in religious communities such as the Ibadan Baptist Conference.

Recommendations

The following recommendations could be helped based on the findings of this study,

1. Integrating religiosity assessment and faith-based into marital support programs within religious institution.
2. Couples in the Ibadan Baptist Conference focus on enhancing communication and emotional expression within their relationships, particularly through joint activities and collaborative projects.
3. Additionally, religious practices and engagement in shared spiritual activities could serve as a supportive mechanism for couples, particularly during times of conflict or marital distress.
4. Churches and religious organizations should consider offering counseling or workshops focused on relationship communication and conflict resolution.

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